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Dynamic Interactions Between Exchange Rate And Economic Growth In Nigeria: Evidence From A Var Model

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ABSTRACT

The relationship between exchange rate and gross domestic product is crucial for understanding of how these variables work in the country to affect the economic activities, thus giving empirical guide for policy formulation. This study empirically models the quarterly gross domestic product and exchange rate from 1986 to 2025 using vector autoregressive model. The time plot of the variables indicated that all the series have trend in them and hence non-stationary. By the Augmented Dickey-fuller and Philip perron unit root test both the series are stationary when adjusted in their first differences. The VAR residual correlation matrix of the variables indicates that gross domestic product is positively correlated with exchange rate and there is present of cointegration among the variables. However, the correlation is slightly negatively high with regards to exchange rate. The study was clear that gross domestic product and exchange rate are determined to be the key economic variable pertaining to the economy of Nigeria. These variables are sensitive and hence affect every sector of the economy. The study also reveals that the existence of exchange rate needs to be monitored. The vector autoregressive model satisfies the stability condition that the Eigen values of the matrix have models less than one. Henceforth, the model is adequate for economic policy in Nigeria and the study recommended that decision makers should critically help streamline the investment patterns of the economy with respect to the economic indicators.

Keywords: VAR Model, Exchange Rate, Gross Domestic Product, Economic Growth, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Comparable many countries, industrialized and developing one of the most fundamental objectives of macro-economic policies in Nigeria is to sustain high economic growth with good measure of economic indicators. There exists a considerable debate regarding the existence of gross domestic product (GDP) and other economic indicators. A consensus exists thus suggesting that macro-economic stability, which is rooted in the spirit of good measure of GDP, is positively related to other economic indicators. Akinbola (2012) implicitly recognizes exchange rate, money supply and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as economic indicators over time.

Multivariate time series (MTS) data are widely available in different fields including medicine, finance, science and engineering. Modeling MTS data effectively is important for many decision-making activities. Consider a time series variable $(y_{1t}) \dots (y_{nt})$. A multivariate time series is the $(n \times 1)$ vector time series $\{y_t\}$ where i^{th} row of (y_{1t}) is (y_{nt}) , that is for any time t , $Y_t = (y_{1t}, y_{2t}, \dots, y_{nt})'$

Multivariate time series analysis is used when one wants to model and explain the interactions and co-movements among a group of time series variables (Economic indicators). Multivariate methods are very important in economics and much less so in other applications of forecasting. The multivariate view is central in economics, where single variables are traditionally viewed in the context of relationship to other variables.

In forecasting an even in economics, multivariate models are convenient in modeling interesting interdependencies and achieve a better fit within a given data or economic indicator. Multivariate forecasting methods rely on models in the statistical sense of the word, though there have been some attempts at generalizing extrapolation methods to the multivariate case. This does not necessarily imply that these methods rely on models with regards to whether they are a theoretical, such as time series models, or structural or theory-based. Much research has gone into the development of ways of analysis multivariate time series (MTS) data in both the statistical and artificial intelligence communities. Statistical Multivariate Time Series modeling methods include the vector Autoregressive process. According to Ansong (2013), an exchange rate is the price of one currency, given in terms of another. The movement of a currency's value relative to others has a profound effect on economies exposed to this currency. Given the interlinked nature of modern economies, exchange rate movements have the power to profoundly affect business, governments, and people around the globe. The spot rate is also referred to as the normal exchange rate.

The statement of the problem is that, in recent study, economic practitioners frequently work with univariate time series models on some economic indicators and many different time series models have been developed to model and forecast economic indicators in the past. Much research has been performed in the modeling of multivariate time series data for forecasting purposes, one area that has been largely overlooked is the time series where the data set consists of a large number of variables and large number of observations on the economic indicators in Nigeria. This research is to address the problems associated in modeling of the economic indicator (exchange rate and gross domestic product) in Nigeria using VAR.

However, the availability of longer and more frequently observed time series emphasize the need for models (economic indicators) which focused on the dynamic structure of the variables. The vector autoregressive (VAR) method corrects the lapses often associated with univariate time series method; one can investigate the relationship between the variables of interest in both short-run and long run.

The VAR model has been developed to address the fact that most questions of interest to empirical macro-economists involve several variables and thus must be addressed using multivariate times series (MTS) methods. Forecasts from VAR models are superior to those from univariate time series models, quite flexible because they can be made conditional on the potential future paths of specified variables in the models.

Recent empirical studies provide mixed evidence on the dynamics between exchange rate and gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Jimoh, Wafure, and El-Yaqub (2026) investigated the impact of financial deepening on economic growth in Nigeria, highlighting persistent inconsistencies despite financial reforms since 1986. They addressed the unclear relationship between key indicators credit to the private sector, money supply, exchange rate, inflation, and interest rate and growth using an ARDL model with bounds testing and ECM on data from 1986–2024. The results showed that money supply and interest rate positively influenced growth in the long run, while credit, exchange rate, and inflation had negative and insignificant effects, with short-run results also indicating negative impacts of money supply and exchange rate, leading to the conclusion that financial deepening had not effectively driven sustained economic growth due to inefficiencies and instability.

Egbaseimokumo (2025) examined Nigeria (1986–2023) using an ARDL framework and found that exchange rate and interest rate significantly drive real GDP, while inflation was insignificant.

Ozigbo, Ekane, and Ujuju (2025), using ECM techniques, reported that exchange rate and interest rate negatively affect growth, while inflation and external reserves positively influence it, recommending production-boosting strategies to complement monetary measures.

Awadzie et al. (2024) applied a Threshold Autoregressive model (1990–2021) and found a nonlinear link: beyond a threshold (8.97%), exchange rate volatility strongly impedes growth. Inflation was regime-dependent, while interest rate effects were weaker.

David (2021) used ARDL and ECM approaches with quarterly data (1981–2020), showing short-run negative effects of interest and inflation on growth, but long-run positive effects of exchange rate, FDI, and current account balance.

Danrими and Badawaire (2025) investigated the interrelationship between GDP growth, population dynamics, and inflation in Nigeria, noting that existing studies failed to adequately integrate population effects into inflation–growth models and to address nonlinear dynamics under structural changes. They reported that the study addressed the problem of weak and incomplete modeling frameworks that ignored population-driven economic effects and lacked robust predictive capabilities. To achieve this, they employed a hybrid methodology combining a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model and machine learning techniques (Random Forest and XGBoost), using annual data from 1960 to 2024, alongside tools such as Granger causality tests, impulse response functions, and forecast evaluation metrics

Michael and Kingdom (2024) looked at Nigeria's trade balance, currency rates, and economic progress. Annual time series data for the years 1981 to 2021 were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistics bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The Heteroskedasticity Model was used in this investigation. The data suggest that the trade balance and currency rate are more sensitive to devalued broadcast. This demonstrates that exchange rate uncertainty has an important effect in pricing adjustments.

Adeniji, K.A. (2024) examined the impact of exchange rate variations on Nigerian commerce using time series analysis spanning 1990 to 2023. The autoregressive distribution lag model (ARDL) was used to investigate the short- and long-term relationships between trade and exchange rate fluctuations in Nigeria. The empirical results demonstrated that excessive exchange rate fluctuations have an impact on Nigeria's economic growth. According to the report, the government should eliminate wasteful spending on unproductive expenditures that provide little or no economic return.

Nyechе (2024) investigated the impact of the exchange rate on economic development in Nigeria from 1985 to 2021. The study used secondary data from the World Development Indicators (WDI) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). It used real GDP as a measure of economic growth. In addition to using the official exchange rate as a proxy for exchange rate dynamics, the study included other domestic characteristics that might influence economic development, such as trade openness and foreign reserves. The study used econometric approaches including unit root tests, cointegration, and autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL)/bound procedures. The results of the bound test revealed a long-run link between economic growth, exchange rate, trade openness, and foreign reserves.

Omoke and Opuala-Charles (2021) looked at the relationship between trade openness and economic development in Nigeria. The study, which took place between 1984 and 2017, employed three indicators of trade openness: total trade, import trade, and export trade. Using the ARDL limits testing method. According to the computations, export commerce greatly enhances economic growth while import trade significantly slows it. According to the evidence, the negative long-term effects of import trade on Nigerian economic growth decrease as institutional quality, or governance quality, improves. The policy implications of these empirical findings for Nigeria are considerable.

Abdul-Razak et al. (2021) investigate the effects of Ghana's exchange rate volatility on international trade by designing import and export equations to estimate short- and long-run using the (GARCH) with (BEKK) specification developed by Engle and Kroner (1995) to ensure the findings' robustness. Monthly data from 1993 to 2017 on Ghana's real effective exchange rates with 143 trading partners were used to predict volatility using the GARCH and EGARCH models. Empirical data reveal that exchange rate volatility has a detrimental influence on export performance in the Ghanaian economy. Thus, the results demonstrate disparities in the direction of the influence of currency rate volatility on imports and exports in the context of the Ghanaian economy.

Adama et al. (2022) investigated the Empirical assessment of the impact of external reserves on economic growth in Nigeria. The researchers investigated how external reserves may assist developing countries in achieving Goal, which calls for the mobilization of extra financial resources from many sources. The study's findings support theoretical assumptions that labor quality has a positive and considerable effect on RGDP. Similarly, capital intensity was demonstrated to have a considerable negative influence on Nigeria's RGDP.

Despite the range of existing studies, gaps persist in understanding how different aspects of exchange rate collectively and individually motivate economic growth across time horizons in Nigeria. Specifically, few studies have simultaneously examined exchange rate and gross domestic product within models that capture both short-run and long-run. Addressing this gap will provide deeper insight into which exchange rate mechanisms are most effective for stimulating growth and which require policy consideration.

Therefore, the interest of this research paper, is to model the economic indicators (exchange rate and gross domestic product) in Nigeria with the approach of vector auto-regressive process detailed on endogenous variable (dependent) over time period from (1986 - 2025) in Nigeria.

Research objectives are to:

- i. Analyze economic indicators in Nigeria using Vector auto-regressive model.
- ii. Determine the estimate parameters of the model.
- iii. Establish model adequacy.

While addressing these, the research paper is significant in Investigating deep into the relationship between exchange rate and GDP in understanding how these variables affect economic activities, thus giving empirical guide for policy formulation. Since in most of the time series univariate studies, exchange rate to economic performance or gross domestic product to economic performance, there is a relatively scanty empirical literature connecting the variables multivariately, this study is meant to fill in the gap on this subject matter. This study will shed light on the determinants of economic performance, which invariably would inform policy makers on which particular policies to adopt to help accelerate and improve the country's economy. It will determine the potential strength of the economic indicator as good predictors of the economic activities and lastly, the findings would perhaps provoke further research in relation to this research, understand past behavior of economic indicators and plan future operations and control its contrary effects.

METHODOLOGY

Estimation of VAR Model

Estimating unrestricted reduced form VAR models is straight forwards computation. James and Watson (2001) standard practice in VAR analysis is to report results from Granger – causality test, impulse responses and forecast error variance decompositions. These statistics are computed automatically (or nearly so) by many econometrics and statistics packages (R, E-views and SPSS). Because of the complicated dynamics in the VAR, these statistics are more informative.

A typical VAR analysis proceeds by specifying and estimating a model and then checking its adequacy. If model defects are detected at the later stage, model revisions are made until a satisfactory model has been found. In order to achieve the objectives of this research a multivariate time series analysis with VAR models can in principle be done with fairly straight forward computation algorithm. Gujarati (2004) VAR methodology superficially resemble simultaneous equation modeling in that it consider several endogenous variables together. But each endogenous variable is explained by its lagged, or past, values and the lagged values of all other endogenous variables in the model, usually, there are no exogenous variables in the model.

The levels VAR Representation

According to Christopher (1980), “if there is true simultaneity among a set of variable, they should all be treated on an equal footing, there should not be any a priori distinction between endogenous and exogenous variables”. It is in this spirit that Sims (1980) developed his VAR model.

The stochastic part y_t is assumed to be generated by a VAR process of order p (VAR (p)) of the form.

$$Y_t = A_1 y_{t-1} + A_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p y_{t-p} + \mu_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

$A_i \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ are $(k \times k)$ parameter matrices.

The error process $\mu_t = (\mu_{1t} \mu_{2t}, \dots, \mu_{kt})'$ is a k – dimensional zero mean white noise process with covariance matrix:

$$E(\mu_t, \mu_t') = \varepsilon_\mu$$

In matrix notations the m time series

$$y_{it}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad \text{and} \quad t = 1, \dots, T$$

Where: t is the common length of the time series.

Then a Vector Autoregressive Model is defined as

$$\begin{pmatrix} Y_{1t} \\ Y_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ Y_{mt} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_1 \\ \mu_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mu_m \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}^{(1)} & A_{12}^{(1)} & A_{1m}^{(1)} \\ A_{21}^{(1)} & A_{22}^{(1)} & A_{2m}^{(1)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ A_{m1}^{(1)} & A_{m1}^{(1)} & A_{mm}^{(1)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_{1,t-1} \\ y_{2,t-1} \\ \vdots \\ y_{m,t-1} \end{pmatrix} \\ + \dots + \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}^{(p)} & A_{12}^{(p)} & A_{1m}^{(p)} \\ A_{21}^{(1)} & A_{22}^{(1)} & A_{2m}^{(p)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ A_{m1}^{(p)} & A_{m1}^{(p)} & A_{mm}^{(p)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_{1,t-p} \\ y_{2,t-p} \\ \vdots \\ y_{m,t-p} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{1t} \\ \varepsilon_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ \varepsilon_{mt} \end{pmatrix}$$

Where:

$Y_t = (y_{1t}, y_{2t}, \dots, y_{mt})'$ denote $(nx1)$ vector of time series variables

A_i are $(n \times n)$ coefficient matrices

ε_t is an $(n \times 1)$ unobservable zero mean white noise vector process.

Model Checking

A typical VAR analysis proceeds by specifying and estimating a model and then checking its adequacy if model defects are detected at the later stage, model revisions are made until a satisfactory model has been found. The wide range of procedures is available for checking the adequacy of VARs and VECMs. Model checking will be applied before a model is used for a specific purpose to ensure that it represent GDP adequately. A number of procedures considers the estimated residuals and checks whether they are in line with the white noise assumption. Another set of tests checks the stability of the model over time. In addition to these more formal procedures exist and also many informal procedures based e.g. on plots of residuals and autocorrelations for some of these procedures, Lutkepohl (2004).

Tests for Residual Autocorrelation

LM Test

The LM test, also known as Breush –Godfrey test for residual auto-correlation of order h may be viewed as a test for zero coefficient matrices in the model (lutkepohl 2007).

$$U_t = B_1 u_{t-1} + \dots + B_h u_{t-h} + i_t \quad \dots (2)$$

The quantity i_t denotes a white noise error term.

Thus, a test of $H_0: B_1 = \dots = B_h = 0$

Versus

$$H_1: B_1 \neq \dots \neq B_h \neq 0$$

is called for the relevant LM statistic can be computed easily by considering the level VAR form.

Testing for Heteroskedasticity in the VAR Model

One of the assumptions for using classical inferences in regression analysis is that the error terms exhibit homoscedasticity or constant variance over time. When modeling multivariate time series systems through vector autoregression, it is important to test if the error terms display heteroskedasticity or non-constant variance. The White test is commonly used to check for heteroskedasticity in the error terms of a VAR specification. It entails an auxiliary regression of the squared residuals on all possible variable cross products:

$$\varepsilon_t^2 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_t + \alpha_2 X_t^2 + \dots + v_t \quad \dots (3)$$

Where:

ε_t^2 represents the squared residuals from the VAR model

X_t is the set of regressors, which includes the lagged values of the endogenous variables and any exogenous variables in the VAR model

X_t^2 represents the cross-products of the regressors

v_t is the error term in the auxiliary regression

The test statistic is then calculated as:

$$F = \frac{(RSS_R - RSS_{UR})/k}{(RSS_{UR}/(T-K-1))} \quad \dots (4)$$

Where:

RSS_R is restricted residual sum of squares from original VAR

RSS_{UR} is unrestricted residual sum of squares from auxiliary regression in (4)

k is the number of regressors in (4)

T is the number of observations

This F-statistic follows an F-distribution with k and $(T - K - 1)$ degrees of freedom.

The null hypothesis is homoscedasticity or constant error variance. Failure to reject the null implies the VAR satisfies this assumption. Corrective measures include weighted least squares or robust standard errors. This ensures inferences from the VAR output are statistically valid and not impacted by heteroskedastic errors. Furthermore, graphical tools, such as displaying the residuals against the fitted values or against time, can give visual insights into heteroskedasticity and aid in the identification of probable patterns or sources of non-constant variance.

Stationarity Test

It is important to first check if the individual time series variables are stationary or contain a unit root. This is tested using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test.

The ADF test regulates a simple autoregressive model of order p for a variable Y_t :

$$\Delta Y_t = \delta Y_{t-1} + \sum \Phi_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (5)$$

Where:

Δ is the difference operator ($\Delta Y_t = Y_t - Y_{t-1}$),

δ is the coefficient on the lagged level, and

Φ_i are coefficients on lagged differences.

The error term ε_t is assumed to be white noise.

The null hypothesis of the ADF test is that $\delta = 0$, meaning the series contains a unit root (is non-stationary). The alternative is $\delta < 0$, indicating the series is stationary (around a deterministic trend or mean). To test the null, the t-statistic of the coefficient δ is calculated and compared to the critical values provided by Dickey and Fuller. If the computed t-stat is lower than the critical value, the null is rejected.

Granger Causality Analysis

One of the main uses of VAR models is that it also opens up the possibility for analyzing the relation between the variables involved. Analyzing the causal relation is of particular interest. Granger (1969) presented a definition of causality in the time series context which has become quite popular in applied work. He called a variable y_{1t} causal for a variable y_{2t} if the information in y_{1t} is helpful for improving the forecasts of y_{2t} .

Empirical Results
Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LNGDP	LNEXCHGRATE
Mean	1.258160	4.445815
Median	1.442216	4.861516
Maximum	2.729757	7.299098
Minimum	-2.797779	0.559616
Std. Dev.	1.060363	1.643492
Skewness	-1.973040	-0.609311
Kurtosis	7.746995	2.755886
Jarque-Bera	55.57053	2.252585
Probability	0.000000	0.324233
Sum	44.03560	155.6035
Sum Sq. Dev.	38.22856	91.83629
Observations	35	35

Source: computed from E-View 10

The descriptive statistics of the variables are presented in table 1. The statistics presents basically the mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis and their respective probability of each series. This is to ascertain the degree of variability in each of the series which is necessary to ensure that they can be used in any analysis. From the analysis, it indicates that both exchange rate and gross domestic product were negatively skewed as at the time of this study. There is variability in the raw data since all of them have different units of measurement. Therefore, there is a need for transformation in order to bring stability in the data and variables of interest. The data was then transformed to the natural logarithm (*ln*).

Trends Analysis

Figure 1: Residuals plot for LNGDP

Figure 2: Residuals plot for LNXCHGRATE

Table 2: VAR Residual Correlation Matrix of the Variables

	LNGDP	LNXCHGRATE
LNGDP	1	-0.5502724984764288

LNXCHGRATE -0.5502724984764288 1

Source: computed from E-View 10

The result in table 2 VAR Residual Correlation Matrix of the Variables indicates that gross domestic product is positively correlated with exchange rate economic indicator. However, the correlation is somewhat negatively high with regards to exchange rate with -0.55027.

Table 3: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
1	-40.30132	NA	0.091298*	3.281579*	3.473555*	3.338664*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

Source: computed from E-View 10

Based on the above summary of the model selection criteria, Table 3 computes various criteria to select the lag order of an unrestricted VAR. The table displays various information criteria for all lags up to the specified maximum (If there are no exogenous variables in the VAR, the lag starts at 1; otherwise, the lag starts at 0.) The table indicates the selected lag from each column criterion by an asterisk “*”.

VAR Residual Heteroskedasticity Test

The VAR Residual Heteroskedasticity Test results, indicate no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity within the residuals, supporting the assumption of constant variance. The joint test yields a Chi-square statistic of 25.11249 with 24 degrees of freedom and a high probability value of 0.3997, suggesting that the null hypothesis of homoscedastic residuals cannot be rejected. Furthermore, the individual component tests for each individual product (res1*res1, res2*res2 and res2*res1) display similarly high probability values (all above 0.05) across both the F-tests and Chi-square tests, confirming the absence of significant heteroskedasticity in each case. These results collectively affirm the presence of constant variance within the model.

Data Analysis and Discussion of Results

Unit Root Test and Vector Autoregression Model were carried out using E-Views 10.0. All the variables were regressed on trend and intercept. It was discovered that the two variables have trend and intercept such as gross domestic product and exchange rate within the period under review.

Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Table 4: Augmented Dickey Fuller Unit Root Stationarity Results

Variables	ADF Statistics	P-Value		Decision	
		I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
LNGDP	-7.074294	0.2806	0.0000	FTR**	Reject*
LNEXCHGRATE	-1.830130	0.3609	0.0000	FTR**	Reject*

Source: computed from E-View 10

Table 5: Phillip –Perron Unit Root Stationarity Results

Variables	PP Statistics	P-Value		Decision	
		I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
LNGDP	-0.905469	0.0689	0.0000	FTR**	Reject*
LNEXCHGRATE	-1.825592	0.3630	0.0000	FTR**	Reject*

Source: computed from E-View 10

Note: [**] means fail to reject the null hypotheses (H₀) that is accepting the null hypotheses (H₀) while [*] means not accepting the null hypotheses (H₀).

The result of the Augmented Dickey-fuller test in table 4 shows that, the two variables (GDP and EXCHGRATE) went through unit root test and they were found to be non-stationary at levels but after first difference all the variables were found be stationary. However, they were statistically significant at 1%. The result of the Augmented Dickey-fuller test suggested that the variables were stationary at first difference because the p-value for all the variables was less than 1% level of significant.

The result of the Philip-Perron test in table 5 shows that, the two variables (GDP and EXCHGRATE) went through unit root test and they were found to be non-stationary at levels but after first difference, all the variables were stationary. However, they were statistically significant at 1%. The result of the Philip-Perron test displays that the variables were stationary at first difference because the p-value for all the variables was less than 1% level of significant.

Cointegration Test

Johansen Cointegration Test

The table 6 below presents the Johansen cointegration test which was carried out in two versions; the

unrestricted cointegration rank test (Trace) and (Maximum Eigenvalue). For Trace, it indicates that series; “None” and “At most 1” with p-values of less than 5% are significant, therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis (H_0) in favor of cointegration for all the series. Thus, the results confirm presence of cointegration among the variables. Subsequently, for Maximum Eigenvalue, it indicates that series; “None” and “At most 1” with p-values of less than 5% are significant, therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis (H_0) in favor of cointegration for all the series. Thus, the results also confirm the presence of cointegration among the variables.

Table 6: Johansen Cointegration Test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)			Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)		
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**	Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	15.49471	0.0009	None *	14.26460	0.0048
At most 1 *	3.841466	0.0174	At most 1	3.841466	0.0174

Source: computed from E-View 10.

Table 7: Granger Causality Test

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.	Decision	Remark
LNEXCHGRATE does not Granger Cause LNGDP	0.84384	0.3661	Accept H_0	causality
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNEXCHGRATE	3.71747	0.0640	Accept H_0	causality

Source: computed from E-View 10

However, as a results of the presence of cointegration among the variables, it is vital to know the important of the variables co-movement. Table 7 above shows that the pairwise Granger Causality test is important for two pairs of the variables measured. As supposed, LNEXCHGRATE does granger cause LNGDP and LNGDP does not granger cause LNEXCHGRATE. So, there is no exist of causality between LNEXCHGRATE and LNGDP. This implies that there is movement among the variables.

Table 8: Vector Autoregressive Estimates

Dependent Variable: LNGDP Method: VAR			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic
LNGDP (-1)	0.039786	0.13851	0.28724
LNEXCHGRATE (-1)	0.088500	0.09634	0.91861
C	0.995645	0.41784	2.38282
R-squared	0.961271		

Source: computed from E-View 10

Table 9: Vector Autoregressive Estimates

Dependent Variable: LNEXCHGRATE Method: VAR			
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic

LNGDP (-1)	-0.101011	0.05239	-1.92807
LNEXCHGRATE (-1)	0.955339	0.03644	26.2166
C	0.512155	0.15805	3.24056
R-squared	0.963853		

Source: computed from E-View 10

Table 10: Estimation Proc:

LS 1 1 LNGDP LNEXCHGRATE

VAR Model:

$$LNGDP = C(1,1)*LNGDP(-1) + C(1,2)*LNEXCHGRATE(-1) + C(1,3)$$

$$LNEXCHGRATE = C(2,1)*LNGDP(-1) + C(2,2)*LNEXCHGRATE(-1) + C(2,3)$$

VAR Model - Substituted Coefficients:

$$LNGDP = 0.0397856614521*LNGDP(-1) + 0.0885001995815*LNEXCHGRATE(-1) + 0.99564481481$$

$$LNEXCHGRATE = -0.101011122193*LNGDP(-1) + 0.955338618562*LNEXCHGRATE(-1) + 0.512154770544$$

The The Vector Autoregression model provides insights into the dynamic relationships between exchange rate and gross domestic product across time lag.

Analysis of VAR Model: LNGDP

Mostly, LNGDP shows great fortitude over time, with a unit increase in LNGDP resulting in a significant of 3.98% increase in the current period. This suggests positive improvement in gross domestic product in the economy. A unit increase in exchange (EXCHGRATE) causes 8.85% increase in gross domestic product (LNGDP). This suggests that the performance of exchange rate has increase over time.

Analysis of VAR Model: LNEXCHGRATE

Also, LNEXCHGRATE shows great willpower over time, with a unit decrease in LNGDP resulting a 10.10% decrease in LNEXCHGRATE, suggesting there is a short fall in exchange rate in the economy and shows negative impact on economic growth. More so, a unit increase in LNEXCHGRATE, with 95.53% increases in LNGDP, this suggests there is increase in overall economic performance.

Table 11: Roots of Characteristic Polynomial

Root	Modulus
0.961825	0.961825
0.368595	0.368595
-0.275217 - 0.149477i	0.313190
-0.275217 + 0.149477i	0.313190

No root lies outside the unit circle.

VAR satisfies the stability condition.

The system is stable at the model 1 of all included variables. The above result indicates that the Eigen values of the system obtainable in modulus lies within the unit circle. The roots of characteristics polynomial do not lie outside the unit circle: Hence from the analysis VAR (1) satisfies the stability condition. The VAR (1) is stable if the roots of

$$\det (I_n - \pi_{12} \dots - \pi_r p) = 0$$

lies outside the complex unit circle (have modulus greater than one) or, equivalently, if the Eigen values of the companion matrix have modulus less than one. AR root table reports the inverse roots of the characteristic AR polynomial. The estimated VAR is stationary if all roots have modulus less than one and lies inside the unit circle.

Figure 3: Inverse Roots of AR characteristic polynomial

Impulse Response of LNGDP and LNXCHGRATE

Figure 4: Impulse Response of LNGDP and LNXCHGRATE

The impulse response functions presented in the graphs above (Fig. 3) illustrate the effect of a one standard deviation shock to gross domestic product (LNGDP) and exchange rate (LNXCHGRATE) on gross domestic product (LNGDP) over a ten-period horizon.

In the left panel, a positive shock to gross domestic product (LNGDP) initially leads to a minor decline in LNGDP. However, as time progresses, the impact shifts, with GDP gradually increasing after period four, showing a positive response in the long term. This suggests an increase in gross domestic product may have a short-term deepening effect on GDP, its long-term impact tends to be favorable.

In the right panel, a positive shock to exchange rate (LNEXCHGRATE) causes a more immediate decrease in GDP in the short run, reaching its lowest point around period's three to four. However, the effect diminishes over time, with GDP returning to near equilibrium levels after the sixth period. This indicates that exchange shocks have a stronger positive impact on GDP in the short term, but the economy appears to adjust and stabilize in the long run.

Both graphs show the dynamic responses of GDP to external shocks in gross domestic product and exchange rate, underscoring the varying short-term and long-term effects of these variables on economic performance.

CONCLUSION

The study "Econometric modelling of Nigeria indicators variable, a vector autoregressive modelling approach." reveals some facts about the economy of Nigeria for the period under examination (1986-2025). A stable model for the vector autoregressive for the two economic variables was obtained. The result of the analysis is unique enough. Therefore, exchange rate reveals weak correlation which signifies the weak and devaluation of the Nigeria currency. The study on the economic indicators was obvious that Gross Domestic product and Exchange Rate are determined to be the key economic variable pertaining to the economy of Nigeria. These variables are sensitive and hence affect every sector of the economy. The study reveals that the existence of exchange rate needs to be monitored.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Lastly, due to the significance and the impact of these economic indicators in Nigeria, some critical steps are recommended based on this study to curb the economic setback. These steps are:

- i. The economic practitioners, CBN and others should oversee the economic variables mentioned in this study as economic indicators in Nigeria.
- ii. The model should be applied in economy policy in Nigeria.
- iii. The monetary policy which affects some of the key economic variables should be redirected.
- iv. Decision makers should critically help streamline the investment patterns of the economy with respect to the economic indicators.

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